

BOURBON MEETS SCOTCH: PRIORITIZING MEDIA MIGRATION BY UNITING TECHNICAL PRIORITISATION WITH ARCHIVAL APPRAISAL

Andrew McDonnell

*University of Kentucky
USA*

*mcdonnell@uky.edu
0009-0009-6501-5581*

Megan Mummey

*University of Kentucky
USA*

*megan.mummey@uky.edu
0009-0007-3371-4965*

Abstract - This paper provides a summary of our work-in-progress to adapt the University of Glasgow Special Collections and Archives' Media Prioritisation Tool to assist in the reappraisal of unmigrated and under-described digital media carriers at the University of Kentucky Libraries. We added an element to this tool that incorporates appraisal criteria, such as archival research value, to our evaluation, as most of the digital media on our shelves meets the Digital Preservation Coalition's definition of practically extinct or critically endangered. We required another criteria to guide the order in which we address the migration and long-term preservation of this born-digital backlog.

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I. INTRODUCTION

This paper summarizes our work at the University of Kentucky Libraries Special Collections Research Center (SCRC) to use and adapt the Media Prioritisation Tool presented by the University of Glasgow's Archives & Special Collections at iPRES 2023 [1].

The University of Kentucky Libraries have been accepting born-digital material in donations and transfers to our manuscripts and university archives collections for decades, but efforts to systematically migrate and process digital records from physical

media began in earnest ten years ago. In the intervening years, a backlog of unprocessed or underprocessed physical media carriers has grown on our shelves, over 2,000 items spread across over 120 separate born-digital and hybrid digital/physical collections.

The Media Prioritisation Tool from the University of Glasgow archivists is a spreadsheet-based calculator that allows staff to enter the media format, age, and storage conditions of a physical media carrier, and in return receive a prioritisation score to determine how swiftly that media should be advanced in the archival processing queue [2]. The tool uses the Digital Preservation Coalition's BitList as its primary underlying criteria for determining the degree of fragility and, in turn, urgency of processing [3].

While the tool proved an ideal starting point for classifying the physical media on our shelves and helping define an argument for significant labor and resources, we found it necessary to adjust a few significant facets of the prioritisation tool when we confronted the realities on our shelves. Most crucially, because of the scale of the necessary reappraisal and processing, we needed to incorporate non-technical criteria in prioritizing the media processing: archival research value.

Throughout all of this work, we use environmental considerations as a guiding light. Inspired by the article, "Toward Environmentally

Sustainable Digital Preservation,” where Keith L. Pendergrass et al., eruditely describe the inherent problem of digital preservation as when “confronted in an environment where staff time is scarcer than digital storage, it can be tempting to appraise digital content in a cursory manner” [4]. Or in other words, to lower the environmental impact of cultural heritage work we should be more selective when appraising born digital records. Due to the covert nature of born digital formats, appraisal processes should be applied at multiple points in the records lifecycle; including acquisition, migration, and processing. Consequently, archivists should be applying appraisal criteria rigorously as a part of prioritizing the migration of born digital materials.

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to reconcile the Bit List-based scoring of the Media Prioritisation Tool (MPT) with the current practical realities of staffing and resources at our institution and the diverse digital appraisal policies and practices that evolved as digital media was acquired across nearly four decades, we needed to adjust some of the assumptions that informed the original MPT.

One assumption implicit in the MPT is that all of the born-digital material on our shelves is of equal research value. While much digital media in our collection is under-described and lacks file manifests, we can make reasonable assumptions about researcher demand for that material based on usage statistics, institutional history, and knowledge of other parts of the relevant media’s collection (in the case of hybrid collections) as well as related materials in other collections.

Another non-technical criterion that determines value to our repository is the degree to which we can share it with the public. Certain unmigrated media on our shelves have unclear or unpromising copyright issues that may limit our institution’s ability to provide access, and in some cases legally or ethically migrate their data into our digital preservation repository. At the other end of the spectrum, as a public institution we have records and materials we are legally mandated to preserve, sometimes indefinitely, a factor we felt was central in defining priority for migration.

We also adapted the prescribed timelines for migration in the original MPT, which slotted at-risk media carriers as needing processing either

immediately, within 3 months, 6 months, 1 year, or 3 years, depending on their format, storage conditions, and age. However, the majority of our media would have fallen into the “immediately” or “within 3 months” categories. This was untenable, and disheartening, with our current staffing, so we abandoned the suggested timeline language, and adapted our tool to rank the priority of media migration, from 1st to 124th.

Otherwise, we maintained the original tool’s focus on evaluating average lifespan of a media carrier’s format, date of creation of media, and the Bit List’s endangered status definitions. We eliminated the MPT criteria accounting for variation in the storage conditions of media, as we determined that conditions have been generally uniform across the collections at our institution.

We retained these original scoring criteria:

- Production score
- BitList score
- Lifespan score [1]

We added to that an Estimated Archival Research Value score that accounts for the expected value of and researcher demand for the data trapped on physical media carriers. We acknowledge that adding a seemingly subjective score to a tool meant to provide objective guidance might appear counter-productive. However, the large percentage of unmigrated materials in our collection that is critically endangered requires additional factors to differentiate their value and determine the order in which they should be processed.

We believe that while it is difficult to quantify an archivist’s understanding of a collection’s research value in a manner uniform across institutions, if our evaluative rubric acknowledges this subjectivity in its language and construction, the tool should serve others’ collections as well as our own with the sort of adjustments we have made to the Glasgow MPT.

III. ESTIMATED ARCHIVAL RESEARCH VALUE

Archival appraisal theory is a complex and multifaceted field, in which one could literally facet and refine criteria forever. However, forced to make choices, we settled on the categories listed in Table 1 as criteria for the Estimated Archival Research Value (EARV) with the intention for them to be broad, simple, flexible, and widely agreed upon in the field of archival appraisal. EARV is to be used pre-

migration with the contextual information available to the archivist at the time of scoring. This contextual information can include but is not limited to the collection description, accession record, donor information, and the original description on the assets themselves.

Table 1. Criteria and Score for Appraisal

Appraisal Criteria	Score
Archival Value (Significance, completeness, credibility, scarcity)	0 = No archival value 1 = Low archival value 2 = Medium archival value 3 = High archival value
Administrative/ Legally Mandated Retention (Is it a permanent record?)	0 = Non-permanent 3 = Permanent
Use and Copyright (Can the institution approve use of the materials? Does the institution own the copyright?)	0 = Copyright status unknown/institution does not own copyright 1 = Institution does not own copyright/owner is known 2 = Institution owns copyright
Institutional Capacity and Cost (Can the institution afford to migrate and preserve these records?; space considerations)	-1 = Preservation exceeds institutional capacity 0 = Neutral cost 1 = Institution can afford to preserve
Duplication (Can the appraiser tell if this is potentially duplicative, either of paper documents or collections at other institutions?)	-1 = Duplicative 0 = Unknown 1 = Likely unique

We approached the task of creating the EARV criteria by reviewing both classic and modern texts concerning traditional appraisal and digital appraisal, such as Frank Boles' works [5], *Appraisal and Acquisition Strategies* edited by Michael Shallcross and Christopher J. Prom [6], and the International Council on Archives Guidelines on Appraisal [7]. These works helped us narrow the criteria down to five. We chose complementary options that define Archival Value, drawing from appraisal concepts such as significance, completeness, credibility, and scarceness, and an Administrative or Legally Mandated Value, which focuses on the difference between a permanent or non-permanent record. The scale we chose in our survey was binary: 0 or 3 for non-permanent or permanent records. However it could be easily adapted to focus on functional analysis with a simple gradient scale.

These criteria can be used together or separately depending on the context of the specific repository. For example, we, as both an institutional repository for the University of Kentucky's records and a large collecting archive, used both categories to appraise university records. However, for manuscript collections we only used Archival Value.

Beyond the concept of value, we included criteria for Use and Copyright, Institutional Capacity and Cost, and Duplication. Archivists must consider practicalities such as use and cost when we preserve any records, not just digital. Duplication must also be considered for the sake of efficiency, both internally and externally, especially when it can be discerned from the label or donor description. Two of the criteria, Institutional Capacity and Cost and Duplication, have negative scoring designed to lower the overall EARV score if the materials are especially problematic for the institution. Use and Copyright treats unknown copyright status or the institution not owning copyright as a zero or neutral rating, since organizations should consider if they can provide permissions for items in their collections. However, we deemed that it did not warrant a negative rating, because at some point most records will enter the public domain (in our national context).

IV. COMBINING EARV & MPT

In practice, we incorporated the Media Prioritisation Tool into our inventory spreadsheet of underprocessed media so that multiple collections could be evaluated and compared in one tool [8].

We added columns for the EARV criteria, and the archivist most familiar with each collection's content, provenance, and research value evaluated the content using that rubric. A basic addition formula in the spreadsheet added the EARV and MPT totals, resulting in final scores that, highest to lowest, guide the order in which we should process material from our born digital backlog.

In practice the combination of EARV and MPT worked very well and gave at times surprising results. The EARV rating never seemed to supersede the MPT rating. Collections rated very highly in EARV could end up farther down on the list due to their MPT score (e.g. a group of floppy disks with a medium EARV could end up higher on the list than a group of CDs or DVDs with a higher EARV.) The Mandated Retention category did privilege our University Archives material over our Manuscript Collections. For many institutions that are both institutional and collecting archives this could be a desirable outcome. In our case, we decided to consider the two groups separately, so that each group gets equal staff resources.

1. V. CONCLUSION

Just as this work builds on the work of others who themselves made use of community-generated resources, this work is open to discussion, feedback, adaptation, and improvement by practitioners everywhere. In keeping with the evolving nature of digital preservation. We acknowledge that our own adaptation is just one step forward in a collective journey.

For the Kentucky Libraries, the tool provided by our counterparts at the University of Glasgow was useful as an appraisal tool and as a means of defining the urgency of the work ahead of us. Faced with thousands of disks, discs, drives, and tapes, knowing where to start and in what order to proceed is crucial. It prevents the sorts of processing paralysis that causes archivists to shuffle material to shelves to be dealt with at an undetermined time, which too easily can become a time that is too late.

Additionally, adapting the tool for archival appraisal beyond technical considerations opened the door for interdepartmental collaboration between the Digital Archivist, Director for Manuscript Collections, and University Archivist to pool their understanding of varied collections. This collective approach has improved the priority we give to

different collections and will help inform the manner by which we appraise and process new additions to our collections moving forward.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Andrew McDonnell is the Digital Archivist for the University of Kentucky Libraries Special Collections Research Center. He has a decade of experience working with digital media and holds a Masters in Library and Information Science from the University of Wisconsin with a concentration in archives.

Megan Mummey is the Director for Manuscript Collections at the University of Kentucky Libraries Special Collections Research Center. She oversees manuscript processing and works with donors to grow the collection. She holds an MSIS from the University of Texas at Austin.

